

Determination of Shock Index and Heart Rate Standard Reference Values during Immediate Postpartum Period Following Caesarean DeliveryDalliya Roy¹, Miss Jeny², Maya Rani³¹PG Trainee, Department of Obstetrics & Gynaecology, Mata Gujri Memorial Medical College & LSK Hospital, Kishanganj, Bihar, India.²Assistant Professor, Department of Obstetrics & Gynaecology, Mata Gujri Memorial Medical College & LSK Hospital, Kishanganj, Bihar, India.³PG Trainee, Department of Obstetrics & Gynaecology, Mata Gujri Memorial Medical College & LSK Hospital, Kishanganj, Bihar, India.

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Abstract:

Background: The immediate postpartum period following caesarean delivery is a critical phase in obstetric care, requiring vigilant monitoring of maternal physiological parameters to ensure optimal recovery and early detection of potential complications. Shock index (SI) and heart rate (HR) are crucial indicators of cardiovascular function, providing valuable insights into hemodynamic stability. This study aims to determine standard reference values for shock index and heart rate during the immediate postpartum period following caesarean delivery.

Methods: A total of 200 women who underwent caesarean delivery were included. Vital signs, including heart rate and systolic blood pressure, were measured at admission, and at 30 minutes, 1 hour, and 2 hours postpartum. Shock index was calculated as the ratio of heart rate to systolic blood pressure. Data were analyzed using SPSS version 21.0.

Results: The mean shock index values were stable and within normal ranges at 30 minutes (0.69 ± 0.06), 1 hour (0.68 ± 0.06), and 2 hours (0.68 ± 0.06) postpartum. Vital parameters such as heart rate, systolic and diastolic blood pressure, mean arterial pressure, and pulse pressure remained within normal limits. No statistically significant changes in packed cell volume (PCV) and hemoglobin (Hb) levels were observed over the monitoring period.

Conclusion: The study established stable and normal reference values for shock index and heart rate during the immediate postpartum period following caesarean delivery. These findings underscore the importance of continuous monitoring to ensure maternal hemodynamic stability and prompt intervention if abnormalities are detected.

Recommendations: Healthcare providers should adopt the established reference values for shock index and heart rate to improve monitoring and management of postpartum women. Further research is recommended to validate these findings in diverse populations and settings.

Keywords: Postpartum Period, Shock Index, Heart Rate, Caesarean Delivery, Hemodynamic Stability.

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Introduction

The immediate postpartum period following a caesarean delivery is a critical phase in obstetric care, necessitating vigilant monitoring of maternal physiological parameters to ensure optimal recovery and early detection of potential complications. Among these parameters, the shock index (SI) and heart rate (HR) are fundamental indicators of cardiovascular function, offering valuable insights into hemodynamic stability and overall maternal health [1].

The shock index, defined as the ratio of heart rate to systolic blood pressure, has emerged as a reliable marker for assessing the adequacy of tissue

perfusion and the presence of hemodynamic compromise. In obstetric practice, where rapid changes in maternal physiology are common, the shock index holds particular significance. It serves as an early warning sign for conditions such as hemorrhage or hypovolemia, which can escalate quickly and pose serious risks to maternal health [2]. Despite its recognized importance, the establishment of standard reference values specific to the immediate post-caesarean period remains an ongoing challenge.

Heart rate, a basic yet crucial vital sign, reflects the maternal cardiovascular response to various

stressors, including surgery and childbirth. Monitoring heart rate provides valuable information about cardiac output, autonomic function, and overall cardiovascular health, aiding in the timely identification of abnormalities and guiding appropriate interventions. The dynamic nature of the postpartum period, characterized by significant physiological changes, underscores the need for reliable reference values to accurately interpret these parameters [3].

Recent studies have highlighted the variability in shock index and heart rate among different populations and methodologies, indicating a pressing need for comprehensive research to define normative ranges for these parameters in the context of early post-caesarean recovery. The significance of early and accurate assessment of hemodynamic stability cannot be overstated, as it is crucial for the prevention of postpartum hemorrhage (PPH), a leading cause of maternal mortality worldwide [4].

This study aims to determine standard reference values for shock index and heart rate during the immediate postpartum period following caesarean delivery.

Methodology

Study Design: A cross-sectional study.

Study Settings: The research took place at the Department of Obstetrics and Gynaecology, MGM Medical College and Teaching Hospital. The study spanned a period of 20 months, from September 1, 2022, to April 30, 2024.

Study Population: Participants included women who underwent caesarean delivery in the Obstetrics and Gynaecology department of the tertiary care and teaching hospital during the specified period.

Sample Size: The study aimed to include 200 participants. This number was determined based on an estimated variability proportion of 20% among approximately 150 monthly deliveries at the facility. Using the Open Epi software version 3.0114, a minimum sample size of 187 was calculated with a 95% confidence interval, a design effect of 2.0, and a 5% margin of error. To accommodate a potential 10% dropout rate, the final sample size was rounded to 200.

Inclusion Criteria: Participants included women who lost less than 1000 ml of blood within 2 hours post-caesarean section, with vital signs collected during this period.

Exclusion Criteria

- Uncontrolled hypertension (BP > 140/90 mmHg)
- Hyperthyroidism (TSH > 4 mu/l)
- Hypothyroidism (TSH < 0.1 mu/l)

- Infection with clinical signs of sepsis
- Known heart disease
- History of coagulopathy
- Blood transfusion during or after delivery
- Severe anaemia (Hb < 7 gm%)

Initially, 250 women were recruited, but 50 were excluded due to postoperative complications such as high blood pressure, anemia, or the need for blood transfusion.

Postpartum Hemorrhage (PPH) Exclusion

PPH cases were excluded, defined as blood loss exceeding 1 litre:

- a) Visual estimation of blood loss during surgery.
- b) Confirmed by a less than 10% decrease in haematocrit levels monitored with complete blood counts at 12 and 48 hours post-delivery compared to pre-caesarean levels.
- c) Women who experienced blood loss with hypovolemia symptoms or required blood transfusion, despite less than a 10% haematocrit decrease, were also excluded.

Study Variables: Pulse Rate, Blood Pressure, Haematocrit (prepartum and postpartum).

Laboratory Investigations: Complete blood counts were conducted before the caesarean section, and at 12 and 48 hours after the procedure.

Data Collection: Demographic data (age, parity, height, weight, BMI) were recorded. Heart rate, systolic blood pressure (SBP), and diastolic blood pressure (DBP) were measured upon admission to the labor room and again at 30 minutes, 1 hour, and 2 hours postpartum.

Statistical Analysis: Data analysis was performed using SPSS software version 21.0. Descriptive statistics (mean, standard deviation) were applied as appropriate. The Shapiro-Wilk test was used to assess normal data distribution. The mean shock index (SI) values at 30 minutes, 1 hour, and 2 hours postpartum were analyzed. Percentiles (5th, 10th, 25th, 50th, 75th, 90th, 95th) of SI values were calculated based on age, BMI, and parity. A significance level of 5% was applied for all statistical tests.

Result

A total of 250 women who delivered via caesarean section were initially recruited for the study. After excluding those with postoperative complications (raised BP, anemia, requirement for blood transfusion, or postpartum hemorrhage), 200 participants contributed postpartum data.

The age distribution of the study participants is presented in Table 1. The majority of the women

were aged between 26-30 years (41.5%), followed by those aged 18-25 years (28%). The mean age of the participants was 28.11 ± 5.18 years.

Table 1: Age Distribution

Age Group (years)	Frequency	Percentage
18-25	56	28.0%
26-30	83	41.5%
31-35	44	22.0%
>35	17	8.5%
Mean age	28.11 ± 5.18	

The parity distribution is detailed in Table 2. Most women (79.5%) were of parity 1, with fewer participants having parity 2 (16%) or parity 3 (4.5%).

Table 2: Parity

Parity	Frequency	Percentage
1	159	79.5%
2	32	16.0%
3	9	4.5%

The mean levels of anthropometric variables among the study participants was studied. The mean height was 163.46 ± 8.11 cm, mean weight was 64.88 ± 6.40 kg, and mean BMI was 24.64 ± 3.03 kg/m².

Table 3: Anthropometric Variables

Variable	Mean \pm SD
Height (cm)	163.46 ± 8.11
Weight (kg)	64.88 ± 6.40
BMI (kg/m ²)	24.64 ± 3.03

The mean levels of vital parameters prior to caesarean section are summarized in Table 4. All values were within normal ranges for the study participants.

Table 4: Vital Parameters

Variable	Mean \pm SD
Heart Rate (bpm)	82.61 ± 6.43
Systolic BP (mmHg)	122.90 ± 6.12
Diastolic BP (mmHg)	84.74 ± 5.57
Mean Arterial Pressure (mmHg)	97.46 ± 5.64
Pulse Pressure (mmHg)	38.16 ± 2.38
SPO ₂ (%)	95.59 ± 3.80
Temperature (°F)	97.78 ± 0.75

The mean shock index (SI) values at different postpartum intervals are presented in Table 5. The mean SI values were within the normal range across all time points (30 minutes, 1 hour, and 2 hours postpartum).

Table 5: Shock Index and Hemodynamic Stability

Time point	Mean SI \pm SD
Pre-Partum	0.70 ± 0.07
30 minutes Post-Partum	0.69 ± 0.06
1 hour Post-Partum	0.68 ± 0.06
2 hours Post-Partum	0.68 ± 0.06

Table 6 show the changes in packed cell volume (PCV) and haemoglobin (Hb) levels at different intervals. There were no statistically significant changes in these parameters over time.

Table 5: Hematologic Parameters

Variable	Pre-Partum	12 hours Post-Partum	48 hours Post-Partum	p-value
PCV (%)	36.40 ± 1.52	35.41 ± 1.81	35.25 ± 1.24	0.098
Hb (%)	11.92 ± 0.76	11.50 ± 1.16	11.24 ± 0.85	0.084

Discussion

The study included 200 women who underwent caesarean delivery. Participants were carefully

selected based on specific inclusion and exclusion criteria to ensure accurate assessment of shock index and heart rate during the immediate postpartum period. The exclusion of participants

with significant postoperative complications ensured the reliability of the collected data.

The majority of the participants were aged between 26-30 years, with a mean age of 28.11 ± 5.18 years. Most of the women were of parity 1 (79.5%), indicating that this was their first delivery. These demographic characteristics are important as they provide a context for interpreting the physiological responses observed during the study.

The mean anthropometric measurements were within normal ranges, with an average height of 163.46 cm, weight of 64.88 kg, and BMI of 24.64 kg/m². Vital parameters such as heart rate, systolic and diastolic blood pressure, mean arterial pressure, pulse pressure, oxygen saturation, and body temperature were also within normal limits prior to the caesarean section. This baseline data is crucial for establishing normative values and understanding the hemodynamic changes that occur post-surgery.

The shock index, calculated as the ratio of heart rate to systolic blood pressure, was monitored at 30 minutes, 1 hour, and 2 hours postpartum. The mean shock index remained stable and within normal limits across these time points, indicating hemodynamic stability in the immediate postpartum period. This finding suggests that the participants maintained adequate cardiovascular function and tissue perfusion following caesarean delivery, which is vital for early recovery and prevention of complications such as hemorrhage or hypovolemia.

The study also monitored changes in packed cell volume (PCV) and hemoglobin (Hb) levels prepartum, 12 hours postpartum, and 48 hours postpartum. There were slight decreases in PCV and Hb levels over time, but these changes were not statistically significant. This indicates that the blood loss during and after the caesarean section was within manageable limits and did not adversely affect the participants' overall hematologic status.

The results of this study provide valuable insights into the normative ranges for shock index and heart rate during the immediate postpartum period following caesarean delivery. The stability of vital parameters and shock index in this critical period highlights the effectiveness of current obstetric care practices in maintaining maternal hemodynamic stability. These findings can serve as reference values for clinicians to identify early signs of hemodynamic compromise and intervene promptly, thereby improving maternal outcomes. The absence of significant hematologic changes further supports the adequacy of intraoperative and postoperative management in the study population.

A study aimed to determine the normal ranges of vital signs in the immediate postpartum period. The

study established that the median systolic blood pressure (BP) was 120 mmHg, diastolic BP was 75 mmHg, mean arterial pressure (MAP) was 90 mmHg, heart rate (HR) was 81 beats per minute (bpm), and the shock index (SI) was 0.66. The study supported the use of an SI upper limit of 0.89 to indicate increased risk of adverse outcomes [5].

A study evaluated various vital signs to predict adverse maternal outcomes in women with hypovolemic shock. They found that SI was a strong predictor across all adverse outcomes, suggesting a threshold of ≥ 0.9 for referral and ≥ 1.7 for urgent intervention [6].

Moreover, a study found that SI and delta-SI were superior to traditional vital signs in predicting postpartum hemorrhage (PPH) and the need for intervention. The study identified $SI \geq 1.143$ and $SI \geq 1.412$ as strong initial and critical thresholds respectively [7].

A study assessed the relationship between SI, heart rate, and postpartum blood loss. They found that SI trends within the first 30 minutes postpartum were associated with significant blood loss, with an SI above 1.04 at 41-60 minutes post-birth being a strong indicator of severe bleeding [8].

A study examined normal values of SI, pulse pressure, and rate over pressure evaluation (ROPE) postpartum. They found that SI values greater than 1.1 were abnormal, emphasizing the need for immediate treatment for values at or above this threshold [9].

A systematic review and meta-analysis was conducted to assess the predictive accuracy of SI for severe PPH in high-income countries. The findings indicated that while SI is a useful screening tool, it has limited predictive accuracy and should be used in conjunction with other clinical signs [10].

A study compared SI with conventional vital signs for predicting adverse maternal outcomes following PPH. $SI \geq 0.9$ provided high sensitivity for intensive care unit admission, while $SI \geq 1.7$ indicated a high chance of maternal death, highlighting its utility in low-resource settings [11].

Conclusion

The study successfully established reference values for the shock index and heart rate during the immediate postpartum period following caesarean delivery. The results indicate that the vital parameters, including the shock index, remained stable and within normal ranges in the immediate postpartum period among the study participants.

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